

THE LINGUISTIC EXPRESSION OF QUANTITY ACROSS LANGUAGES

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Annotation. *To summarize what we have discussed, we can conclude that the concept of quantity, as an element of cognition, has evolved through several stages and has reached its today's form. The various phases in the development of this concept, from sensory perception to abstract visualization, are still evident in modern language.*

When examining how quantity is expressed in language, one important aspect to consider is that, when the number of items in a set is small enough to fit within the first decimal range, it is processed more quickly through emotional and visual imagery. Most researchers agree that people can understand and remember certain sets of objects without needing to attentively count them.

The development of different forms of the concept of quantity is closely linked to the progression of cognitive understanding, following the natural laws of cognitive development. "Evidence from the ethnography of primitive societies, as well as data from diverse languages around the world, suggests that the stages of quantitative comprehension in human perception are mainly the same across different cultures, aside from minor differences." The typological research of world languages helps not only to clarify the stages of the concept of quantity in Turkish cognition but also to trace the origins of numbers, which are linguistic representations of quantity, and the development of plural suffixes. The scope of typological linguistics in this area is large. This phenomenon, observed in Azerbaijani Turkish, is similarly present in other Turkic languages.

When it comes to expressing the concept of quantity, Turkish languages are on par with other advanced languages worldwide and are not behind in terms of the variety of ways the concept is conveyed. The fact that Turkish languages can represent a wide range of quantities also reflects the advancement of the quantitative category in Turkish thought and the overall development of these languages.

Key words: *numerical value, measurable amount, quantity, plurality.*

In the majority of the world's languages, nouns are marked for singular and plural forms. The semantic distinction between these two categories is generally straightforward: singular denotes one entity, whereas plural indicates more than one, as in “table – tables”. However, linguistic reality is often more complex. In English, the category of number in nouns raises a number of important issues. For example, there is a semantic difference between the phrases “three houses” and “three hours”. The first example refers to three distinct objects existing side by side, while the latter designates a continuous, uninterrupted temporal span.

At times, plural forms are encountered in nouns that are normally uncountable. In such cases, the plural does not signal a simple increase in number but rather introduces a shift in meaning. Consider the noun “water”: in the meanings such as “the waters of the Atlantic” or Jack London's “A Daughter of the Snows”, the plural form conveys a notion quite different from

its singular counterpart. Crucially, it would be ungrammatical to quantify these with numerals (“three waters” or “three snows” in the literal sense). Instead, the plural “waters” typically denotes a vast body of water, such as an ocean, while “snows” may describe extensive snow-covered regions, as in the Arctic. Moreover, the phrase “the water of the Atlantic” emphasizes the chemical or physical composition of that water, whereas “the waters of the Atlantic” expresses a geographical or territorial concept. These examples show that the use of singular and plural forms can generate distinct semantic interpretations, sometimes diverging so significantly that the plural acquires a meaning absent from the singular. A case in point is “colours”, the plural of “colour”, which can denote a flag, as in “to serve under the colours of liberty” [7; 88].

From a historical perspective, early human thought appears to have conceived collections of objects not as the sum of individual items, but rather as unified wholes. The focus was less on numerical quantity and more on qualitative features of the group. Collective nouns were thus likely understood as designations of qualities rather than mere counts. L. Lévy-Bruhl notes that in primitive cognition, each set of objects was preserved in memory with remarkable precision, and any absence within such a set was immediately perceived [12; 164].

The representation of collections of objects differs across languages. According to V. I. Degtyarov, ancient written monuments of the Slavic languages demonstrate that the nomenclature of nouns was conveyed primarily through special collective nouns, which themselves occurred in the grammatical singular. Degtyarov observes that, in general, word-formative suffixes rather than inflectional suffixes were employed to denote sets of nouns, or else collectiveness was expressed through lexical means. At a later stage in the development of the Slavic languages, markers of collectiveness gradually came to function as grammatical plural forms [3; 59]. These facts indicate that the collective aspect of the category of quantity served as the foundation for the emergence of its other formal and semantic shades.

V. Z. Panfilov identifies a number of archaic affixes expressing collectiveness in the Nivkh language, such as “-m / -v, -sk / -ks, -rk / -kr”, and others [12; 251]. Turkologists note that in the Turkic languages, the notion of collectiveness is largely preserved in toponyms and ethnonyms. However, suffixes found in these forms were also extended to ordinary nouns in order to denote the plural. In Turkic, collectiveness is thus primarily expressed by lexical (e.g., “herd”) and lexico-syntactic constructions (e.g., “large–small, old–young”).

The grammatical expression of collectiveness varies across languages, manifesting in both singular and plural forms. This flexibility reflects the inherent contradiction in the concept of collectiveness. O. Jespersen observes that “logically, collectiveness should be understood as one on the one hand, and as a whole on the other” [7; 225]. Even when conceived as singular, collectiveness simultaneously implies a unity composed of discrete parts. Jespersen further stresses that collectiveness “should be used only to express the unity of countable nouns.” Similarly, V. F. Asmus claims that “in fact, the unity of a collective entity arises from the plural; it is not an actual singularity, but rather a form of plurality” [1; 37]. Since a set inherently consists of distinct elements, it may be regarded as a manifestation of divisible quantity.

Within this framework, one may also distinguish such varieties of divisible quantity as the indefinite plural, the abstract plural, and the concrete plural, all of which are expressed in Turkic languages through the same grammatical markers. At the same time, languages differentiate between divisible and indivisible quantities. Indivisible sets are realized in nouns that denote materials or substances, such as “water, aluminum, oil, iron”, and similar entities. Unlike discrete objects, such materials exist physically but resist direct quantification.

These nouns do not evoke the image of a specific object but rather function as properties or qualities of things. For instance, the word “door” denotes an object with a concrete form, recognizable features, and a defined function. By contrast, the word “iron” does not directly conjure a single object; instead, it generates a range of associations— “iron doors, iron dishes, iron beds”, and so forth. As F. de Saussure observed, such words produce different associations for different individuals. Hence, concepts denoting material or natural substances tend to function more as qualities than as discrete objects. It is no coincidence that these nouns frequently appear as attributive elements modifying other nouns to specify their characteristics.

For this reason, concepts denoting material substances may be regarded as designations of qualities. In such cases, quantity manifests itself analogously to quality: it is determined not by countability but by extent or measure. This raises the question of how languages express the quantity of uncountable entities.

In many languages, nouns referring to material substances occur only in the singular. For instance, English has “water, milk, meat”; French has “lait” (“milk”), “viande” (“meat”); and German has “Butter” (“butter”), “Milch” (“milk”), “Fleisch” (“meat”). A similar pattern is observed in modern Turkic languages. Yet in the early stages of Turkic, even nouns denoting uncountable substances bore quantitative markers: “süt” (“milk”), “örten” (“fire”), “ozan” (“tea”). The final consonants in these nouns represent ancient plural markers preserved as relics. Of particular interest is the process by which uncountable nouns acquired quantitative markers, a development often attributed to the proto-Turkic or even earlier stages. Evidence from Mongolic supports this view: in Mongolian, “süt” (“milk”) is historically a plural form derived from the root “sün” with the suffix “-t” [8; 19].

Unlike many other languages, Turkic reveals morphological markers for both divisible and indivisible quantities. This suggests that the ancient Turks possessed a nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the category of quantity. Moreover, plural suffixes are not the sole means of expressing plurality. Just as nouns may convey collectiveness without affixation, they may also take on special grammatical suffixes to signal related meanings. Compare, for example: “student – students – studentship”.

In the language of the ancient Turkic written monuments, this form of plural is also attested. In these texts, the suffixes “-egu” and “-egun” serve to form collective plurals. Mammadov notes that bulk numbers formed with these suffixes appear only twice in the monument dedicated to Tonyukuk. For example: “Tabgach, Oghuz, Kitan, these three truths “If the Chinese, Oghuz, and Kitan unite in three ...”” (Tone 12); and “The trio said, ‘Let us unite in a trinity, let us destroy it’” (Tone 21) [10; 62].

The development of collective numerals is also observed in the language of the Uyghur written monuments of the 11th–15th centuries. V. M. Nasilov, who studied these texts, explains that in this period numerals could take the suffixes “-aqu / -equ” to form collective numbers. Among his examples are forms derived from “one” and “two,” glossed as “all together” [11; 45]. Although the suffixes “-egü / -egün”, which produced collective numerals, were rarely used in earlier monuments, their functions expanded in the subsequent development of the Turkic languages. This becomes particularly evident when comparing ancient Turkic monuments with modern Turkic varieties. For instance, L. V. Dmitriyeva, in her study of the Baraba Tatar language, shows that bulk numerals are formed with the suffixes “-av” and “-au” [4; 213].

In the modern Tatar literary language, collective numbers are formed by adding the suffixes “-au, -au” to numerals. According to N. K. Dmitriyev, “the semantics of collective

numbers are summarized in a certain concentration of objects formed by the addition of individual units.” In Tatar, collective numbers built with “-au, -au” are restricted to numerals from one to ten. With higher numerals, collective meanings may be expressed through additional suffixes such as “-lap / -lep, -laşın / -leşin”. These retain their basic quantitative functions but also develop new semantic and stylistic nuances: they may express reciprocity, unity, or even emphasize the abundance of objects or individuals within a set.

In modern Nogai, collective numbers refer to the plural of certain objects and persons. The suffix -ov / -ev is added to quantity numbers to form such numbers. However, it should be noted that, unlike the Tatar language, in the Nogai language these suffixes are multiplied by numbers from one to seven, as well as by the number nine [2, 154].

It can be assumed that in the early stages of the development of Turkic languages, collective numbers were not characteristic of Turkic languages. As a result, the suffix that forms a community in the language of the ancient Turkish written monuments known to us is found only in the monument written in honor of Tonyukuk. Apparently, this is why individual nouns can express the plural and the plural without taking any suffixes. Because it is a well-known fact that in the language of ancient Turkish written monuments, plural suffixes are rarely used.

The list of plural nouns in English includes a number of sciences (for example, riyaziyyat - mathematics, fizika - physics, fonetika - phonetics, siyasət - politics, etc.) and disease names (for example, qızılça - measles, məxmərək - mummy, raxit - rickets, etc.) can be added. The reason for this is that when we say mathematics, the word includes a number of different scientific disciplines. In another example, we can see this in the name of measles. The disease occurs in the form of numerous inflammatory rashes on the skin, and this set manifests itself in the name of the disease. But as in the case of phonetics, in some cases it is impossible to understand the cause of this plural.

Sometimes, expressions expressing the concept of plural are treated as a single principle in a sentence. For example, when the term United Nations is used in a sentence, the noun is expressed in the singular form of the predicative (The United Nations is a world organization).

A number of nouns denoting a group of people or animals can be used in two forms in a language. They represent either a group representing a community or members of that group.

For example, in the sentence “My family is small”, the adjective small refers to an entire family. “My family are good speakers” says that every member of the family is a good speaker. The same rule can be applied to the sentence “The cattle were grazing in the field”.

Recently, another idea about the number category in nouns was put forward by A.Isachenko. According to him, the main meaning of this category is not quantity, but discreteness. For example, in English, the word scissors is a plural, but the reason for its plural is that it consists of two inseparable parts. The word itself is unique as an object. But the same suffix (houses) in the word indicates the plural form of a specific noun, and here we are talking about individual houses [6; 44].

Collective numerals are also attested in languages outside the Turkic family. For example, in the Okhotsk dialect of Even, special collective numerals are used to count both humans and inanimate objects, expressing their unity and integrity. In this system, collectives are formed exclusively by attaching the suffixes “-ridur / -nidur” to numerals within the first decimal range.

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